

Frame Structure Of Mental Vocabulary Of The Kazakh Language

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Abstract

The article discusses the semantic nature, expressing mental values, mental lexemes are few in number and are characterized by an extensive semantic structure and ambiguity. The processes of semantic evolution in the lexical system of language come from the ideological, spiritual and cultural experience of the people and are due to the cognitive and discursive activities of the nation. Verb, as the most extensive and complex part of speech, which characterizes the signs and attitudes of the objects of the world. The multifaceted interaction of language, thinking and reality is provided by the functional-semantic approach to the description of the verbal system, which enables the systematization of all types of knowledge related to the cognitive and communicative human activity and embedded in the semantics of the verbal units. Mental verbs (nominations) in the Turkic languages and in the Kazakh language have a complex semantic structure containing conceptual and figurative components, the implementation of which reflects models describing fragments of human mental and emotional activity.

Introduction

As M. Minsky, who introduced the term *frame*, shows: “Frame is a structure for imagining stereotypical situations. Different information is associated with each frame” [11, p. 7]. The correspondent considers two types of frames, which are now called *static* (frames) and *dynamic* (scripts) in linguistic usage. Any type of frame defines the necessary structural information of the sub-object. However, in the intellectual system, not only numerical measurements of many characteristic features are functioning, but also *symbolic information* (visual image). Here it can be explained by a system of experimental or phenomenally effective thinking of mankind. In fact, it involves a specific linguistic structure in the *perception, storage of information, thinking* and communication for processes for the formation of structural units.

Cognitive model is formed through human thinking activities. The degree of formation of the content of the name of a word or phenomenon in the human mind is reflected in this **cognitive model**. Therefore, it should be understood as the formation of language content. The cognitive model is created by the symbols and units that make up the information encoded in the language content. The units and symbols that organize **the cognitive model** in consciousness are: **association, stereotype, symbol, image**. *Association* is formed on the basis of the connection between people's long-standing experiences and new concepts. Frames are made up of *cells* where information is stored. They are arranged in a certain step(stage) order. The information of cells of a higher stage is easily perceived by the sensory organs of man. These objects can have appearance, type, size, taste and other information. The middle cells store information that can be selected as needed. At the lower stage, information is collected related to encyclopedic knowledge about objects that are not immediately visible in perception. Each frame is both large and *complex structure*. In linguistics, a frame is used to explain the transfer of knowledge about different stereotypical situations in a language. In addition, due to the fact that each linguistic symbol provides a fund of knowledge about a particular object, it is possible to consider them as a frame.

The role of frame structure in the formation of derivative words and the development of semantics, the creation of semantic fields is significant, and is directly related to the processes of thinking, association. The language preserves the goals of national consciousness, the way of thinking, the behavior of each people. The word is stored in the lexical fund and is used not only as a conceptual symbol in the speech process, but also carries a constant load of associative thinking. Therefore, the fact that the word undergoes various semantic changes, coincides with another concept, the emergence of polysemy, figurative meanings is directly related to these laws. It is also effective in describing the process of metaphorization without separating linguistic and extralinguistic data. Cognitively, a metaphor is recognized as a conditional action between two frames. The first *base-frame* corresponds to the significant descriptor of metaphor, the second *purpose-frame* is considered to be a denotative descriptor [15, p. 31]. The *base-frame* represents the symbol needed for the metaphorical pattern. As a result of the analogy, the symbol is converted to the *purpose-frame*.

Theory. Frames are an organized fund of ideas about our world. Information in any consciousness is stored in memory by a certain system, that is, this information has high or low characters. Scenarios collect a lot of pockets of information. But a person does not need all that information at once, each piece of information is taken from the database according to its needs. That is, concepts are created for a specific purpose, based on other concepts. This purpose can be *nominative, expressive, pragmatic*.

Ch. Fillmore states about frames: “We can use the term frame to define categories and names in the language system, their lexical and grammatical features” [15, p. 36]. In the cognitive consideration of the creation of the name, the words that are the basis for the creation of the name are taken as the **base-frame**, the result of metaphors is taken as the **purpose-frame**. In derivative words, a connection appears between at least two frames. Their ability to create an example (model) can also be said to depend on the information in the frame knowledge base. “Words from a linguistic frame activate in the speaker’s mind the whole frame and the scheme associated with it; schemes can be used as an instrument for constructing blocks for constructing a text model, that is, a model of the world compatible with text” [15, p. 34]. The symbols used in the nomination of the idea in this opinion - linguistic units, as a certain system, structure, which accumulates the knowledge base, stimulate the creation of other nominations with the necessary information in the human mind. Therefore, words used in lexical units are recognized as frames.

The verbs in the Kazakh language have different semantic meanings and are words in the language that mean movement, action, process, various changes, phenomena. Y. Mamanov gives the definition “A verb is a part of speech that represents the names of various processes taking place in the form of an action or movement: according to the meaning, they are divided into several groups by their main characteristics” [10, p. 35-36] and divides them into 8 groups. In fact, “the verb does not mean the name of the action, but action itself, only some parts of the verb mean the name of the action (action name or infinitive). The semantic field of the verb is wide. “The reason for this, says A. Iskakov, is that semantics are not only the action of the subject, but also include all concepts related to such processes as a multitude of actions, movements, activities, states, situations, which are found in nature, in public life, born of abstract human thinking and consciousness. This rich semantics of the verb, its variety, is always associated with the concept of time or tense” [18, p. 233]. Verbs can be divided into several groups depending on their semantic and functional nature. For example: When A. Iskakov divided them into: verbs of action, verbs of movement (*roll over, translate, advance*), verbs of state (stative) (*lie down, stand up*), verbs of think-speech (*speak, learn*), verbs of growth (*propagate, bloom*), orientation verbs (*go, get out, take away*), visual-auditory verbs, behavioral verbs [18, p. 235], in academic grammar:

1. Verbs denoting actions directly related to the object: (*eat, drink, oil, go, look, read*) and other transitive verbs.

2. Verbs denoting the movement, tendency, direction of the subject: (*come, go, get down, get out, clean up, comb, diverge*).

3. Verbs related to the state of the subject, the process of qualitative change: (*sleep, wake up, decrease, increase*).

4. Descriptive verbs: (*look, smile, whisper, blush, sing*)

5. Intransitive verbs with internal object: (*foal, bloom*), [6, p. 127-128].

Results and discussion. Linguistic units have two sides. One is the *personal* (sound cover) side, the other is *the internal content, the semantic side*. The word and its meaning are two sides of the same coin. These two are inextricably linked. Here they play a leading, key role. Because without meaning there is no word, without word there is no meaning. In linguistics, the semantic side of the word is studied in the field of *semasiology*. It studies the meaning of the word, its types, structure, patterns of formation, development, causes, methods of defining the meaning of the word.

Research method. The structure of the meaning of the verb. In linguistics, “emotionality” - (lat. *Emovere* - seduce, excite) fr. *emation* - different moods, feelings, influence of a person on the environment [8, p. 432]. Whereas emotional vocabulary is explained as the use of many meanings like: sympathize and embarrass, alert and joy, anxiety and hatred, fear and courage, faith and unbelief, sadness and excitement, boredom, and *expressiveness* is a generalized form of semantic style features of linguistic units. It is used as a linguistic tool to express the speaker's attitude and opinion to the content of the word or to the *addressee* (person) to whom the word is addressed. It has phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic tools. Through these tools, it acquires the ability to express the mental and emotional state of the speaker. *Emotion* conveys the spoken word as an emotionally (sensitive) *clear* (affective) word. It is said that the means of emotions are studied in phonetics, grammar, lexicology, stylistics and semantics [8, p. 432].

Specialist of the Sakha (Yakut) language L.N. Kharitonov, depending on the lexical and semantic nature, features of grammatical structure, classified verbs into three groups: 1) state verbs, 2) imitative verbs and 3) figurative verbs [16, p. 15]. G.K. Kuliev in his work classifies Azerbaijani verbs into 12 groups [5]., S.A. Rzayev in his dissertation “Semantic categories of verbs in the modern Azerbaijani literary language” - divided the verbs into 8 groups [12].

Just as all verbs can be semantically grouped based on their semantic features, uses, and characteristics, internally synonymous verbs can be grouped according to their semantic field and meaning. Because it is obvious that the meaning of a word is related to each other, however, each of the different words has a figurative meaning in context. The word is an important linguistic unit, which means the phenomena of society and nature, the spiritual life of man. As a word is a complex phenomenon, the meaning and semantics of a word is a complex category. It is complex and difficult to discover the meanings of synonymous words and to group them. In this regard, the concept of synonymous words should be determined based on the concept of scientists. Saying that “The integrity of the language, its national identity appear in the organic connection of the semantic side of the word, on the one hand, and the word itself (i.e. sound) on the other. And therefore, it is clear that the lexical richness of a particular language is measured both by the codicism of words and their semantic functions”, S. Kenesbaev said that most words are semantically contradictory, and there is a slight semantic difference between them [4, p. 275-277].

There are several principles in the division of words into lexical and semantic groups, which have long been established in linguistics. For example, words that belong to the same lexical-semantic group: a) interconnection with the help of *certain semantic units* (semes). b) *belong to one part of speech that can create a certain paradigmatic sequence*; the fact that words considered to be a unit of LSG (lexical semantic group) are connected with other words, while maintaining their independence; that they complement and unite each other in meaning, etc. From this point of view, there are many thoughts and opinions about synonyms and their definitions. Definition by Professor A. Bolganbaev corresponding to the nature of the Kazakh language: “Synonyms are words that occur in one part of speech, although they are pronounced in different ways, but they have similar meanings, but each has its own semantic, stylistic or emotional differences”. This concept [1] given by him *approaches the semantic field*.

M.D. Chertykova divides mental verbs in the Khakas language into sub-semantic classifications (LSG):

- 1) verbs of knowledge (pil “to know”);
- 2) verbs of thinking (sagyn “to think”);
- 3) verbs of understanding (onna “to understand”);
- 4) verbs of faith (kyrtin “to believe”);
- 5) verbs of doubt (ikinchile “to doubt”);
- 6) verbs of opinion (sana “to hold”);
- 7) verbs of mental abilities (ygren “to learn”, hygyr “to read”, etc.);
- 8) verbs of assessment (paala “to assess”);
- 9) single mental verbs [17, p. 82-100].

N.K. Dmitriev was the first to group and comment on the lexical and semantic system of words in the Turkic languages, taking into account its features [3]. He wrote an article based on the material of the Tatar language, studying the verbs of *thinking, speaking, movement* as an individual group. Following the example of the scientist, a number of scientific works were published. In those works, verbs are divided into the following groups according to their meaning: verbs of movement, verbs of action, verbs of speech, verbs of perception and sensory, verbs of state [14].

When grouping words (verbs) by semantics, within the meaning, the basic principle is the specificity of each word, its features, meaning in context, function, functional use. And the meaning was taken as a key feature in determining the main features of the semantics of verbs in the language. Because the main features of the verb are clearly visible in the semantics. Knowledge of the semantics of verbs is of great theoretical and practical importance in the grouping of verbs according to their semantic unification. For example, according to the concept of T.V. Bulygina “Mental verbs can indicate a particular mental state (*to know, to believe, to remember*), mental activity, usually aimed at gaining knowledge (*to think, to ponder*), or indicate the emergence of a certain mental state as a result of a previous activity or sudden insight (*to learn, to guess, to understand*)” [2, p. 31] one can recognize the mental state through the act of thinking.

Experiment. In Kazakh linguistics there are many difficulties in classifying verbs, as the semantic grouping of verbs is incomplete. Since this topic is the subject of research, the main purpose was to reveal the semantic field of verbs, their meaning, to conditionally divide them into groups in terms of internal meaning. For this, *based on the systems adopted* in linguistics and Turkology, recognized as *principles*, relying on and taking as a basis the linguistic data of the Kazakh language, based on the characteristics of the Kazakh language, selecting and analyzing verbs in the dictionary of the Kazakh literary language and synonymous dictionaries by meaning, classifying them by specificity of use, according to semantic features, they are conditionally divided **into the semantic field** of the following verbs:

1. Verbs denoting action and movement: *bicker - grab - fight, salute - greet - shake hands - welcome, save - free - let go, jump - bob up and down.*
2. Verbs expressing feelings, moods: *see - watch - notice - observe - scout, believe - trust, feel - know, cry - sob - blubber - moan - bitterly cry, miss - languish - crave - desire, afraid - fear.*
3. Verbs denoting state: *expect - wait, accelerate - increase - expand - strengthen.*

4. Verbs that represent the image: *close the eyes partly - squint - narrow, wheeze - moan - groan, brattle - rumble - knock - crack, vapor - rumble - blatter, embarrass - make blush, growl - grumble.*

5. Verbs denoting the process of quality (state) or sign: *troop off - move away - alienate, become obsolete - frazzle - decay, mold - sprout.*

6. **Verbs related to thinking:** *understand - get into shape, think - remember - recollect;*

7. Subjective verbs: *boast - swagger, considered it insufficient - take it small - neglect - not be satisfied, pretend to be care - pretend to be sympathize.*

8. Verbs related to speech: *say - speak - tell, talk - discuss - consult, murmur - mutter.*

Mental verbs related to thinking. The meaning of the verbs in this group is closely related to thinking, that is, to the activity of the human brain. Therefore, the verbs belonging to this group can be conditionally called logical-psychological. Things and phenomena that cannot be known directly in reality can only be known through thinking. Thinking is a general and indirect verbal representation of the relationship of objects and phenomena of the external world in the brain, consciousness. Verbs related to thinking are semantically different from other groups of verbs and are less numerous. These verbs are associated with the words *perceive the world, accept, understand, comprehend, feel, know*, and represent the process by which thought passes through meaningful thought. A person's thoughts and actions are reflected in the solution of various problems by adapting them to each other. Verbs related to thinking are few in number but wide in meaning. The first person who studied the verbs of thinking in Turkic studies and give a scientific opinion was Professor N.K. Dmitriev [3]. From this period, all journalists, who divided verbs into lexical and semantic groups, consider them as a separate group. In a new direction, the study of their connection with the national worldview, the semantic field has recently attracted the attention of journalists, and in Turkic studies began to study individual semantic groups of verbs. The object of a comprehensive study of these verbs has not yet been fully considered. In Russian linguistics, mental verbs as a semantic group have become the subject of several studies and began to be studied in a new direction. Although the principles of division of general words into lexical and semantic groups are the same, it is clear that each language has its own national features [9]. It refers to the process of thinking in which the verbs of **mental thinking** are directly related to the processes of thinking. Thus, in terms of meaning, it is connected with stative verbs. Verbs such as **think, cogitate, know, feel, understand, comprehend, recognize** are used as *semantic fields* in the verb of **thinking** in language. For example, For several days Abai *cogitated* very hard and *thought* alone (The path of Abai II, p. 10). ... *makes you feel* his strong anxiety (The path of Abai, II, p. 9).

Researcher of verb semantics in the Azerbaijani language G.K. Kuliev states that the verbs of thinking are connected with the process of human thinking: "Verbs of thinking. This LSG of verbs denotes the mental processes of man. It is divided into two LSFs:

a) LSF of the verbs of thinking with the meaning of the thinking process: Azerb. *dgigun-*; gag. *dushun-*; **oilan-** *to think, reflect, cogitate*"; azerb. *to invent, think out*. in this meaning in the Turkmen language the verb *tosla-* is used.

b) LSF of the verbs of thinking with meaning, the result of a mental act: Azerbaid, Turk., gag. **san-**; tur. *osm - "believe, suppose, think, consider"* [5] dividing the verb of thinking into two subgroups. These mental verbs are closely related to the semantic series of *cognition, perception, understanding, comprehension, sensation, cognition of the world* and represent a process that occurs through the thought that synonymous to **thinking**.

For example, academician A. Kaidar gives several meanings to the words *oi, tus, bil-*: 1. **Thought** [oi] I *thought, idea, intention* [7, p. 265].

EC/ES 1. memory - kar., kbal., kir., kaz., nog., kkal., tat., bash., uz., uigh., lob., alt., chuv., Budagov I, USp., KW : memory of something - uz. ;

2. Intellect - ktat., kar., kbal., kir., kaz., nog., kkal., tat., bash., uz., uigh., lob., alt., chuv., P 869,870. Budagov I, USp. ; thinking - P I1523;

3. Mind - ktat., kar., kbal., nog., uz., uigh., P I869, KW, Vámbéry ĆSpr. reason - kaz., nog., uigh.; consciousness - kar., kir., kkal., tat., bash., Uz., dial. Y. Gulyamov, alt., Joki W. ;

4. attention - kar., kuz., dial. Chor. Sh.24;

5. imagination - kir., kkal., alt.;

6. thought - kar.;

7. sense - kaz., tat., bash., alt., Budagov I, Abû H [13, ESTYA, p 306].

2.*Tus [tüs] IV: *tusin- <tus + in - understand, comprehend. tuy> tuisik* [p 290.]. **3. Bil-** [bil-] II 1) *know, understand, find out*; 2) *find out*; 3) *master, assimilate* [p 199.]. Of these meanings, the meanings from series I, IV, II correspond to [7, p. 275].

Know(bil)=verb. 1. *Be aware of something.* 2. *In the sense of "remember"(keep in mind).* Сен аттың жөнсіз оқ, Тәңірі – қазы, Тас – таразы, тентекті сұрамас деп қалма. Серт бұзғанның, бил, орны шоқ (You shot inappropriately, God is the judge, Stone is the scales, do not think that they will not ask from the mischief. Know, that the one who breaks the oath has a place on fire) (Abai, Collection of works). 3. *The forms -a, -e, -y is*

attached to the main verb and means to be able, ready, able to do. 4. Find a solution, master the method. Түйеге салды қасқыр ауыздығын, *Билмейді қай жерінен бауыздарын.* (The wolf put the bit into the mouth of a camel, does not know where to slaughter it). (K. Azirbayev). 5. Understand, comprehend. 6. Define, determine, investigate, find out. 7. Observe, feel, dawn upon, think through. 8. Recognize, know by sight. 9. Evaluate, appreciate, deprive, separate. 10. Make a choice, come to a decision. Таңдау жасау, бір шешімге келу. Сонда шал мына сөзге аң-таң қылды, не қыларын *біле* алмай, аз ойланды. (Then the old man was surprised by these words, not knowing what to do, he thought a little). (Abai, Collection of works), Dictionary of the Kazakh literary language].

Meaning of movement verbs: **White**[aq] I white; figur. milk, dairy products, etc. *ақ [aq] II (imitative: something white, whitish): aqi- <aq+yi look viciously, sparkling with the whites of the eyes. aq I. ақ-[aq-] III flow, take course; rill; figur. to flow, elapse (about a process, event, walking, speech); *ақ- [aq] IV (let go, release, give free rein): aqyt- <aq+yt- untie, unfasten, unleash; *ақ- [aq] V: aqtar<aq+tar- rake up, sorting out; leaf through; rummage. aq-III; ақ [aq] VI ar. 1) true; 2) innocent; 3) inevitably. aq XII; *ақ [aq] VII: aqta <aq+a sync. Castrate, geld(horses, camels) // castrated, gelding (horse, gelded horse, atan camel) [7, p. 186].

A:K/ A:G I Turk.; ақ/aq ktat., kar. k., kbal., kir., kaz., nog., tat., bash., uigh., alt., tuv., DTS₄₈, Malov₃₅₉, Kāšǵ. D.15₁₅, Analyt. In. ₄₆₅, KW₃₉, i.e.

1. white - in all sources; *whiteness* - turk., tur., kbal., alt.; *albugo* - turk., tur., az., uz.; *the white* (for example, eyes, eggs) - tur., az., kar., kir., uz., khak., tuv.; *fair* - tat., khak.; *silver, gray* - turk., kar., t., kbal., tat., bash., uz., khak., tuv., Budagov I₆₆, *gray hair* - turk., uz., *blonde* - khak., *pale* - tat.; *milk, dairy products* - kbal., kir., kaz., bash.; *thin white paper matter, linen fabric* - az., kum.;

2. *clean* (directly and figuratively) - turk., tur., kbal., kaz., tat., bash., uigh., Kāšǵ. D.; *virgin, innocent, spotless* - turk., tur., kar., kaz., tat., bash., uig.; *innocence, sinlessness* - tur., alt; *honest* - kir., kaz.; *correct* - gag., *good-natured, upright* - kar.;

3. beautiful, wonderful, luxurious, magnificent - khak. [13, p. 116-117].

A:K/ A:Q II turk., ktat., cum., kar., kaz., nog., bash., DTS₄₈, Malov₃₅₉, Kāšǵ. D.₁₅, Analyt. In.₄₆₅, KW₃₉; From the above data it follows that in the Turkic languages there are two forms of the basis under consideration, one with a wide one, the other with a narrow non-labial vowel, formally *ak-* should be considered ancient than *yk-*, since the second form, judging by the monuments, does not appear, seems, earlier than Chagatai texts. However, the verb root *yk-* together with the nominal root *yk*, like the verb root *ak-* together with the nominal root *ak*, form verbal-nominal homomorphic pairs “name-verb”, formed according to the oldest, preliterate word-formation model, and therefore all four roots have to be considered as the oldest, in which the broad root vowel alternates with the root narrow vowel, as in a number of other roots.

1. *to be carried away by water, stream-* az., kum., alt., khak.; *flow-, leak-, stream-* in all the above sources; *spill* - turk., kum.; *pour, flush* (liquid) - uz. dial.; 2. *to be carried away by water, stream-* az., kum., alt., khak.; 3. *crumble, flow* (about granular materials) - chuv.; secondary and figurative meanings; 4. *shift eyes from object to object*; 5. *secretly get out, get away* - PI₉₅. [13, p.118-119].

Conclusion. Thus, based on the views of scholars on the analyzed mental verbs, they were divided into groups according to their semantics, general semantic unification. However, in general, depending on the semantics of mental verbs in the Kazakh language, it should not be assumed that there is only the above type. Since it is just as difficult to classify the meanings of mental verbs, also determining their meaning and grouping them according to their meaning is a complex linguistic phenomenon. Each word has a wide range of meanings and uses. Therefore, this classification is not limited to the problem of grouping mental verbs. Their various types and meanings are still being discovered, and their identification and grouping will be gradually improved. The problem of grouping is not only mental verbs in the language, but also general common verbs in their semantics, the sequence is not yet formed, so the given classification must be conditionally accepted as a variant, based on the scholars' grouping.

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